

Supplementary File 3. Checklist of 13 items for evaluating the risk of bias in individual studies

Items	Evaluation criteria
(A) Randomization	If there was a description of appropriate method of randomization, such as random number generation, the bias was judged as (+). In the case of non-randomized study or inappropriate randomization method (such as a quasi-randomized controlled trial), or no description of randomization method, the bias was judged as (−).
(B) Concealment of allocation	If the researchers were not informed of the allocation until the start of the study, the bias was judged as (+). If there was no description of the concealment of allocation or the researchers were aware of the allocation, the bias was judged as (−).
(C) Similarity of baseline	If there was no statistically significant difference in the primary outcome between the groups at the baseline, the bias was judged as (+). If there was a statistically significant difference in the primary outcome between the groups at the baseline, or no statement of a significant difference, the bias was judged as (−).
(D) Blinding of participants	If the study participants were completely blinded, the bias was judged as (+). If the study participants were not blinded or there was no description of blindness, the bias was judged as (−). In the case of double-blind studies, participants were judged to be blinded.
(E) Blinding of care providers	If the care providers (e.g. the person who handed the test food to the participant) were blinded, the bias was judged as (+). If the care providers were not blinded or there is no description of blindness, the bias was judged as (−).
(F) Blinding of outcome assessors	If the outcome assessors were blinded, or in the case of outsourced analysis of samples (e.g. blood sample) or quantitative analysis using equipment without any subjective influence, the bias was judged as (+). If the outcome assessors interviewed the participants and asked them to answer, or if the outcome assessor directly scored their performance, the bias was judged as (−). In the case of a double-blind study, the outcome assessors were judged to be blinded.
(G) Cointervention	If the participants of both groups received the same additional intervention or no additional intervention, the bias was judged as (+). If only the participants of the intervention group or the control group received an additional intervention, the bias was judged as (−).
(H) Compliance	If the intake rate of the test food was not reported, or if the intake rate of all groups was low (80% or less), or if one group had a notably lower intake rate than the other groups (a difference of 10% or more), the bias was judged as (−). If the intake rate of the test food was reported and the above did not apply, the bias was judged as (+).
(I) Rate of drop-out	If dropout rate was 10% or more in any or all groups, the bias was judged as (−). If there were no dropouts or the above did not apply, the bias was judged as (+).
(J) Intention To Treat (ITT) analysis	The bias was judged as (+) for ITT or Full Analysis Set (FAS) analyses and (−) for Per Protocol Set (PPS) analyses.
(K) Outcome assessment timing	If there was a clear time difference in the timing of the measurements of outcomes between the groups, the bias was judged as (−). If there was no difference in the timing of the measurements (e.g. parallel group comparative study), the bias was judged as (+).
(L) Selective outcome reporting	If the study plan was registered in a clinical trial registry and all outcomes planned at the time of registration were reported, the bias was judged as (+). If the study plan was not registered in a clinical trial registry or not all outcomes planned were reported, the bias was judged as (−).
(M) Other potential bias sources	For example, the bias of a study that only reported the results of a stratified analysis of specific subjects was judged as (−). If no bias other than the 12 items above was suggested, the bias was judged as (+).